

Corrosion of 63/37 Brass in Citric Acid Solution and Its Inhibition by Azole Type Compounds

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Manuscript received 13 February 1975, accepted 5 July 1977

The inhibitory action of imidazole, benzimidazole, 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and 2-mercaptobenzothiazole towards corrosion of brass in 0.1 M citric acid was investigated. The inhibitory power of these compounds was found in the following order:

Most of the compounds are able to form complexes with copper or/and zinc ions. The higher protection afforded by 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and 2-mercaptobenzothiazole may be due to formation of insoluble visible, adherent film on the copper surface. I.R. spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{MBT})_2$ complex has been taken for the explanation of chelate formation.

1-2% citric acid is used as a cleaning agent for boiler at 45° in the presence of inhibitors¹. Desai² reported the inhibitory action of gelatine towards corrosion of 63/37 brass in citric acid solution. Donaldson³ reported the inhibitory action of benzotriazole towards corrosion of copper in citric acid. Citric acid is used as a automatic dish washers with detergent.

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the inhibitory action of some azoles towards corrosion of 63/37 brass in 0.2M citric acid solution.

Experimental

Brass (63/37) specimens were cold rolled and annealed at 550°. Rectangular specimens of size 6×3 cm (24 S.W.G.) were used. The composition of 63/37 brass was found as follows:

Experiments were carried out at 22±1°. 250 ml of 0.2M citric acid (BDH grade) was taken for the immersion of each specimen. The solution of citric acid was prepared in distilled water and solutions of inhibitors were prepared in ethanol. The procedures for preparation of specimen, testing and cleaning were adopted as described by Champion⁴.

Results and Discussion

Results on weight loss are given in Table 1. Citric acid was found as a moderate corrosive agent for 63/37 brass.

TABLE 1

Reagents	Cu ⁺⁺ Colour of the precipitates	Zn ⁺⁺ the precipitates
Imidazole	Soluble dark blue coloured ppt	White insoluble ppt
Benzimidazole	No ppt	No ppt
2-mercaptobenzimidazole	Dull yellow	Light white ppt
2-mercaptobenzothiazole	Dark yellow	Light yellow amorphous

In the case of imidazole almost acceleration was observed. It afforded only 18% protection at its highest concentration i.e., $5.88 \times 10^{-3} M$. Benzimidazole afforded highest 33% protection at $3.42 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentration. Its inhibitory action slightly increases with increase in concentration of the compound. 2-Mercaptobenzimidazole was found very effective inhibitor at its $2.67 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentration. Its inhibitory action remarkably increases with increase in concentration of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole. In the case of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole 91% protection was noted at $2.39 \times 10^{-4} M$ concentration. Its inhibitory action slightly improved with increase in concentration of the compound. It afforded 99% inhibition at its $2.39 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentration. The inhibitory action of above stated compounds may be arranged as follows.

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The compounds studied in the present investigation have the following structural formula.

Imidazole

Benzimidazole

2-Mercaptobenzimidazole

2-Mercaptobenzothiazole

It is well known that thiazoles are excellent chelating agent for copper and zinc ions. Large volume of work has been done on azoles, particularly benzothiazole and 2-mercaptobenzothiazole as inhibitors for copper and its alloys in immersed and atmospheric conditions. The attachment of azoles with metal surface and the strength of metal inhibitor bond decides the effectiveness of the inhibitor. 2-MBT at its lowest concentration 1-10 ppm effectively retards the corrosion of copper in cooling tower system, and has hence been used nowadays⁵⁻⁸. Inder Singh⁹ *et al.* reported the dissolution of mild steel in H_2SO_4 at 40° with and without 2-MBT. The corrosion rate, corrosion potential, anodic and cathodic polarization and H_2 -absorption and permeability have been also studied.

In other series of experiment the inhibitors were tested as a chelating agents for copper and zinc ions which are the main constituents of 63/37 brass.

From the weight loss data it is clear that imidazole and benzimidazole are poor corrosion inhibitors while 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and 2-mercaptobenzothiazole effectively retard the rate of corrosion. The above table indicates the complex forming tendency of the latter two compounds with Cu^{++}

and Zn^{+2} ions. From potentiometric analysis of the complex with Cu^{+2} and Zn^{+2} ions, it is found that solubility of copper complexes is less than that of zinc complex. The solubility product for $Cu(2-MBT)_2$ complex is found to be 3.5×10^{-2} , while $Zn(2-MBT)_2$ complex is soluble to appreciable extent.

In aqueous solution 2-mercaptobenzothiazole ionizes as a weak acid. The ionic component forms insoluble salts with copper ions and conceivably the protective coating consists merely of the insoluble copper salt of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole. However, a more possible structure for the protective coating would take into account the fact that the 2-mercaptobenzothiazole possesses not only a ring sulphur, both capable of forming co-ordinate bonds with the metal ion.

The infra-red spectra of analytically prepared $Cu(2-MBT)_2$ complex indicates the covalent bonding between copper ion and 2-MBT which is through sulphur of the -SH group and a co-ordinate bond from sulphur which is in the thiazole ring. The I.R. spectra of $Cu(2-MBT)_2$ gives sharp band for stretching frequency of C-S at 1050 cm^{-1} and bending doublet for C-S at 740 cm^{-1} and 765 cm^{-1} . There is no SH band between 2600 and 2550 cm^{-1} .

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